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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE BANKING SECTOR IN KAZAKHSTAN

Abstract. The article discusses the digital transformations taking place in the financial sector, which are caused by modern problems and opportunities of the entire industry, concerns whether it is insurance, retail, banking or other financial services. Technologies have long become an integral part of the development of the financial sector, and the attitude towards them on the part of banking structures is gradually changing. Today, according to World Bank and ID Finance, the penetration rate of fintech in China is 69%, in Russia – 43%, in Kazakhstan – 21%, so we can talk about serious growth potential. For Kazakhstan, the topic of redistribution of the translation market against the background of the development of digital services is relevant. Over the past three years, transfers by bank details have given way to online transfers by card number, and now the latter are being actively replaced by transfers by phone number. Now transfers by phone number to another bank are possible only for clients of financial institutions who have joined the Sunqar instant payment system. Another technological topic that almost all market participants are working on is digital biometric customer identification. At the beginning of the year, the National Bank announced the launch of a project for remote identification of STB clients and announced a proposal to create an Identity Exchange Center. The article provides an analysis of the comparison of technology implementation in Russia and Kazakhstan. Unlike their Russian counterparts, Kazakh banks are not yet very active in introducing digital services such as online chats with a live person, providing a unified history of transactions for all products, and managing products and limits. The processes of consolidation and consolidation will continue in the banking sector, but according to experts, the emergence of new players in the banking market, including foreign ones, is not expected, since the general economic crisis has affected everyone.

Keywords: Bank, new technologies, digitalization, financial institution, biometric identification.

Technologies have long become an integral part of the development of the financial sector, and the attitude towards them on the part of banking structures is gradually changing. Several years ago, the top priority was the question of the benefits of a particular service for the bank itself. Today, when the lines between banks and tech companies are blurring, and the functionality of most digital services is becoming more and more identical, the issue of value for the client comes to the fore. However, financial structures have something to strive for in this area.

A long period of technology adoption is in the past; the easier and faster the adaptation of the client to the new service, the higher loyalty can be expected. According to the data announced at the recent Profit Finance Day conference in Almaty, by 2035, 90% of all transactions will be carried out

using online services, up to 30% of funds will be allocated using online services, and the task of banks is to be in time in order to find place in the changing realities. Today, according to World Bank and ID Finance, the penetration rate of fintech in China is 69%, in Russia – 43%, in Kazakhstan – 21%, so we can talk about serious growth potential. The question is how effectively this potential will be realized (<https://nationalbank.kz/kz?switch=russian>).

The launch of ApplePay has become one of the most anticipated events and a challenge for the traditional market. According to the data announced during the MoneyDay banking conference, after the introduction of ApplePay in Kazakhstan, the number and volume of non-cash transactions among customers who started using this function have doubled. Opinions are mixed here. Some market participants see a threat in the further expansion of Apple, which announced its intention to release its own virtual card and strengthen its position in the fintech segment. Others believe that the growth in the penetration of ApplePay QR payments is mainly due to the so-called early adopters, who previously preferred non-cash payments. In a global sense, both banks and new form factors pursue a common goal – the fight against cash.

In recent years, banks around the world have spent significant amounts of money on building a digital foundation. But digital transformation doesn't happen by itself. Banks have yet to learn how to effectively work with “dark data” – for example, with archives of communication with customers by phone, chat and e-mail, audio recordings of the interaction of tellers with branch visitors, full-text documents, user comments on social networks and even with images from cameras observations capable of capturing customer emotions ...

Most banks in Russia have adopted the concept of a digital office and are moving in this direction with varying degrees of success, moreover the most notable results being achieved by small regional banks.

For the Russian Federation, the emergence of the first “bank without offices” – “Tinkoff Bank” in the banking system was a good incentive; the Internet telecommunications concept of interaction and the concept of “without visiting a branch” with clients coincided with the time and the necessary level of technological development of technology and communication methods.

In Kazakhstan, Kaspi accounts for over two-thirds of the digital banking market.

For Kazakhstan, the topic of redistribution of the transaction market against the background of the development of digital services is relevant. Over the past three years, transfers by bank details have given way to online transfers by card number, and now the latter are being actively replaced by transfers by phone number. The tool called “transfer by phone number to Kaspi” is actively used not only by individuals, but also by small entrepreneurs, and this “gray” niche in the future will be occupied by either a bank or a system of instant payments.

Now transfers by phone number to another bank are possible only for clients of financial institutions who have joined the Sunqar instant payment system. This service was launched in February 2019, and in five months, according to the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 270 million tenge was transferred through the system. So far, three banks have joined Sunqar. Major players, noting such advantages as responsiveness, low commissions and transaction costs, point to imperfections in the system, in particular, regarding dispute resolution and identification.

Digital biometric customer identification is another technological topic that almost all market participants are working on. At the beginning of the year, the National Bank announced the launch of a project for remote identification of STB clients and announced a proposal to create an Identity Exchange Center. As conceived by the developers, the system will allow clients to receive financial services in a remote format – to open bank accounts, deposits, and issue payment cards.

The development of the direction of digital biometric identification is inextricably linked with the need to ensure security, and here risks cannot be excluded.

The state and the banking sector are two industries that set the tone for digitalization in Kazakhstan. Speaking about second-tier banks from the point of view of information security (IS), three categories can be distinguished:

1. about 20% chose a systematic progressive path of development, implying digitalization, coupled with a good state of information security;
2. 50% – banks that live in the hype format are very technologically advanced, but information security is a little behind there;
3. for the rest, the issue of providing information security is very painful.

Today, cybercriminals are actively working on creating digital twins, analyzing data from our computers and mobile devices, and a resource for selling digital personalities operates in the darknet.

The aggregate of data about us as solvent individuals is growing, and a person who can buy our digital twin will be able to perform any actions on our behalf.

So far, according to the Marksw Webb research, only AltynBank can fully remotely identify the client. In the applications of AltynBank, ForteBank and Sberbank, consumer can remotely change the client's personal data, use banking products, reissue the card and order official documents. In the mobile application of BCC and Eurasian, it became possible to open a current account in tenge or currency; Kaspi, BCC, HomeCredit and Eurasian – open a deposit; Eurasian, BCC, Sberbank – open a debit card. Unlike their Russian counterparts, Kazakh banks are not yet very active in introducing digital services such as online chats with a live person, providing a unified history of transactions for all products, and managing products and limits. Some banks have too complicated the procedure for correcting personal data, especially when it comes to changing the phone number.

The processes of consolidation and enlargement will continue in the banking sector, but according to experts, the emergence of new players in the banking market, including foreign ones, is not expected, since the general economic crisis has affected everyone. 2021 will be the year of recovery for both the global economy and Kazakhstan. Everyone will try to reach the indicators of 2019, but, most likely, they will be lower (<https://kursiv.kz>).

The most affected industries are tourism (air carriers), small business, oil producers (due to falling prices and global demand). In general, the expectations are such that 20–40% of all those who have received an extension will come for a new restructuring.

Banks will need to create additional provisions in the absence of additional sources of income, and therefore the overall profitability is likely to decline. The hardest hit will be those who actively lend unsecured loans, businesses associated with trading houses, restaurants, travel, sports, cinemas and entertainment services (<https://www.banker.kz>).

Almost all market participants will continue to invest in technology, developing the level of digitalization. Each financial institution will offer a variety of services ranging from lucrative credit and debit cards to contactless payment technologies for goods and services.

In general, the global economy may begin its recovery by the end of 2021, including in Kazakhstan.

“Coronacrisis” pushed Kazakh banks to develop digital services. If earlier they offered online the same services that were available in the branches, now they are introducing new ones. This is how digital banks are born – a new generation of financial institutions.

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